

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF MANGO "CHEP", THE EXUDATION OF THE FRUIT OF *MANGIFERA INDICA*.

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The fresh mango "chep" in liquid condition as well as the semisolid mango chep resin have been investigated. The odorous principle present in the fresh chep could not be isolated by steam distillation which appears to destroy it. From the dry mango chep a resin (mangiferen) $C_{21}H_{34}O$ a resinous acid (mangiferic acid) $C_{46}H_{76}O_4$, and a resinol (mangiferol) $(C_{21}H_{34}O)_2$, have been isolated and studied. Contrary to expectations, these resinous principles are found to be not allied to bhilawanol or anacardic acid. The degradation and oxidation products of mangiferen, which has been more fully investigated largely bring out their close relationship to the abietic acid series of resins, and supported the recent view of resins being condensation products of isopren

When the mango fruit is detached from its stem, a thin fluid exudes from it, which resembles turpentine in odour and consistency and soon dries up to a straw coloured, translucent, semi-solid mass which slowly loses its odorous character. It is known in vernacular as 'Am ki Chep' and is popularly regarded as a cure for scabies and other cutaneous affections. This reputed medicinal property, along with the fact that in its fluid condition, the mango 'chep' is known to have vesicating properties, suggested to us the possibility of its chemical constituents being similar in composition to the various resinous principles obtained from the Anacardiaceae family of plants (to which mango belongs), which have vesicating properties and are considered in indigenous medicine as cures for skin affections. Two of the cases in point are the juice of the pericarp of the 'marking nut' (*Semecarpus anacardium*, Linn.) which was found by Pillay and Siddiqui (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667) to consist chiefly of a vesicating principle, bhilawanol, whose formula was established by them as and

the juice from the pericarp of cashew nut (*Anacardium occidentale*, Linn.) consisting of anacardic acid as one of its constituents, which was found by Pillay (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 226) to differ from bhilawanol only in the substitution of one of its hydroxyl groups by a carboxyl. It, therefore, appeared of great interest to us to investigate, if the mango 'chep' also

contained a similar resinous principle with a long, unsaturated, normal side-chain, attached to a catechol or salicylic acid nucleus.

It may be noted here that mango gum resin from the bark is stated by Hooper (*J. Pharm.*, 1907 *iv*, 24, 718) to contain 79% of resin. According to Lemeland (*Pharm. J. Chem.*, 1904, *vi*, 19, 584) the gum resin contains 60% water-insoluble and 40% water-soluble matter. No work, however, had so far been done on the mango 'chep' resin.

As a result of our investigation we have isolated from the dry chep the following three products, through a long drawn out process of separation, ensuring the standard of uniformity which may be acceptable in the chemical characterisation of resinous products.

(1) A resen, $C_{21}H_{34}O$, which distils constantly to a straw coloured brittle mass at $308-10^{\circ}/5$ mm., begins to soften at 60° and melts at $63-65^{\circ}$. $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +60^{\circ}$ in 1% absolute alcoholic solution, yield 16% on the weight of the ether extract of the mango chep, and 4.5% of the semi-solid chep. We have given it the name "mangiferen".

(2) An acid, $C_{40}H_{60}O_4$, which melted slowly at $68-70^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +32^{\circ}$ in 1% alcoholic solution which we have named "mangiferic acid", yield 2% of the ethereal extract.

(3) A phenol ($C_{21}H_{36}O_2$)₆, which gives greenish violet colouration with ferric chloride and a white precipitate with lead acetate and to which we have given the name "mangiferol." yield 3%.

Although the analytical values of the products noted above further strengthened the expectation of their being closely related to the products isolated from *Semecarpus anacardium*, a closer study of their chemical character, particularly of the chief constituent mangiferen, which was more fully investigated, definitely negatived this view.

Mangiferen gave negative results when tested for active H after the method of Zerewitinoff and formed no benzoyl, acetyl or naphthylisocyanate derivatives. No methoxy group was found to be present after the method of Zeisel. It was left unaffected by caustic potash fusion at 220° and by concentrated sulphuric acid and also concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.4). Its extreme indifference to chemical reagents as brought out by these observations clearly goes to show that mangiferen is a resen.

In so far as resens are known to be chemically indifferent products and their uniformity in most of the cases mentioned in literature is rightly considered doubtful*, the following observations made by us on mangiferen will appear to be of special interest.

* This fact has been particularly well brought out in a recent communication on the resen of the Manila-Eleemi resin by Bauer and Starcke (*Arch. pharm.*, 1934, 279, 167).

1. Mangiferen gives an oxidation product, $C_{21}H_{34}O_2$, when treated with a large excess of potassium permanganate (in acetone solution).

2. On dry distillation and subsequent fractionation of the distillate over sodium, two hydrocarbons answering to the molecular formulæ $C_{15}H_{26}$ and $C_{17}H_{34}$ were obtained.

This point is of special significance in so far as resens have more recently been variously indicated as isoprene condensation products (Wagner-Jauregg, *Annalen*, 1932, 496, 52 ; Bauer and Umbach, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 794).

3. On treatment with fuming nitric acid, it yielded an acid which was not sufficient in quantity for more complete investigation but whose analysis indicated that it might be a saturated dicarboxylic acid, $C_8H_{12}O_4$, like the racemic *trans*-hexahydrophthalic acid, obtained by Levy (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 81, 150,) through a similar oxidation of abietic acid.

The water-soluble portion of dry mango chep consisted of gums, etc., and contained no tannic or gallic acids.

Fresh mango chep was worked on the same lines as detailed in the case of dry chep, and was found to yield similar fractions. In contrast to the dry chep, the ether extract of the fresh chep had the characteristic odour of the freshly detached mango, but no essential oil could be obtained from it through steam distillation which apparently destroyed the odorous principle.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mango chep (500 g.) was collected during the mango season from several large consignments of mangoes, through special arrangements made by Hakim Zafar Khan Sahib. We take this opportunity to express our thanks for the pains he took in this connection, without which it would not have been possible to carry out the present investigation.

Separation of the Constituents of "Mango Chep."

The mango chep thus collected (500 g.) formed a semi-solid sticky mass. It was divided into water-soluble and ether-soluble fractions. The ether-soluble part (150 g.) was then taken up in alcohol and treated with an excess of alcoholic lead acetate solution. The filtrate was made ammoniacal, allowed to settle and filtered from the lead salt. The clear filtrate was delead with hydrogen sulphide and the residue left on removal of the solvent was taken up in petroleum ether and treated with caustic soda, when a small quantity of a black sticky matter settled down. The straw

coloured filtrate was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and finally with water, was dried over sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent, when it yielded 25 g. of an extremely sticky straw coloured product. (Found : C, 82.9 ; H, 11.2 per cent).

This neutral matter (1 g.) was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction was analysed. (Found : C, 83.0 ; H, 11.7 per cent). Having thus ascertained that no intrinsic change takes place by distillation in *vacuo* the remaining quantity (24 g.) was subjected to fractional distillation in *vacuo* whereby four fractions were separated. The third and main fraction was redistilled, when *mangiferen* was obtained as a straw coloured product (20 g.), distilling at 308-12°/5 mm. (main quantity at 310°).

The lead salt from the ether extract of the chep was exhaustively extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was well shaken up with hydrochloric acid to remove the lead, washed well with water, dried over sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent. For complete removal of any neutral matter from this residue, it was once again purified through the lead salt as described above, and then taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was treated with 5% caustic soda solution in a separating funnel, when a pink coloured granular middle layer sharply isolated itself from the ether layer above and the alkaline solution below. After repeatedly washing this layer with ether and 5% caustic soda solution, it was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the presence of ether, the clear ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent. The sticky residue was then repeatedly washed with boiling petroleum ether when it was reduced to a buff coloured light powder (14 g.). By a series of fractional precipitations with benzene and petroleum ether, 3 g. of *mangiferic acid* was finally obtained as the petroleum ether-insoluble and benzene-soluble fraction.

The petroleum ether-soluble, acidic fractions from the above were taken up in ether and exhausted with 0.5% caustic soda solution. The pink, alkaline solution was repeatedly washed with ether. It was then freed of dissolved ether on the water-bath, filtered after cooling, acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried and freed of the solvent. The residue (about 12 g.) was once again purified through the lead salt when *mangiferol* was finally obtained as a reddish brown, petroleum ether-soluble treacle (5 g.). Several intermediate fractions, apparently mixtures of mangiferic acid and mangiferol, were not pursued further.

Characterisation of the Constituents.

Mangiferen ($C_{21}H_{34}O$).—As obtained by distillation it forms a straw coloured brittle mass. On precipitation of this product from its alcoholic solution with water it forms a white powder. Both these samples show the same optical activity $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +60^\circ$ in 1% absolute alcoholic solution. It begins to soften at 60° , melts at $63-65^\circ$ and is soluble in all common organic solvents from which, however, mangiferen could not be induced to crystallise. [Found: C, 82.9, 82.9, 83.1, 83.7; H, 11.0, 11.2, 11.6, 11.7; mean. C, 83.2; H, 11.4; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 336. $C_{21}H_{34}O$ requires C, 83.4; H, 11.3%; M. W. 302; $C_{21}H_{32}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 10.6%). It gave no colour with ferric chloride or precipitate with basic lead acetate. It contained no hydroxyl group as was shown firstly by the negative result of active hydrogen estimation after Zerewitinoff and secondly by its failure to form an acetyl or a naphthylurethane derivative. Methoxy group also was found to be absent as tested after Zeisel. After stocking for a year, mangiferen showed the same optical activity, but it began to soften at 63° and melted completely only at 90° . Mangiferen dissolves to a deep golden yellow solution in concentrated sulphuric acid, which later turns orange. On dilution the original product is recovered from this solution even after heating it on the water-bath for some time. On addition of a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid to a solution of mangiferen in acetic anhydride a blood red colouration is produced, which darkens on standing taking on a brownish yellow tinge. Fusion with caustic potash at 220° yielded back the original product unaffected.

Oxidation of Mangiferen with Potassium Permanganate: Oxymangiferen ($C_{21}H_{34}O_2$).—To mangiferen (2 g.) dissolved in acetone (200 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.) was added slowly with stirring and occasional warming on the water-bath, potassium permanganate (7 g.) dissolved in acetone (200 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.). On working up the reaction product no acid could be separated, most of the substance having remained unreacted. This was subsequently treated with twice the above quantity of potassium permanganate in the same concentration. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate freed from acetone on the water-bath. The residue was treated with dilute alkali and extracted with ether. The alkali-soluble portion did not yield any appreciable acid fraction on acidification. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute alkali, then acid and finally with water, dried over sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent. The treacly residue was exhausted with petroleum ether to remove the unreacted neutral matter. The petroleum ether-insoluble residue was obtained as a

colourless light powder on complete removal of the solvent in *vacuo*. Oxymangiferen thus obtained, melted at 85°. Like mangiferen it gave no colouration with ferric chloride and no precipitate with basic lead acetate. (Found: C, 79.3; H, 10.3. $C_{21}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 79.2; H, 10.7 per cent. $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 79.8; H, 10.1 per cent). Oxymangiferen appears to have been formed through the subsequent splitting of a molecule thus of water from the initial product ($C_{21}H_{36}O_3$) of the permanganate oxidation of mangiferen.

Dry Distillation of Mangiferen.

Mangiferen (5 g.) was heated at ordinary pressure when it distilled to a reddish brown jelly like substance contaminated with a few drops of water. On repeated fractional distillation of this distillate an oily liquid (0.5 g) distilling at 218-21° separated. (Found: C, 87.4, H, 9.9 per cent). Another fraction (about 0.5 g.) distilling at 278-80° was of a thicker consistency. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 10.4 per cent). As an oxygen-free substance at this stage could not be isolated, the various distillates were combined together and distilled over sodium and the distillate again fractionally distilled, when two main fractions distilling at 225-35° and 260-70° and showing $n_D^{20} = 1.4970$, and 1.5155 respectively were obtained. 0.1010 G. of the lower boiling fraction took up 0.1386 g. of bromine in chloroform solution in cold as against 0.1581 g. required by $C_{15}H_{26}$ for two double bonds. (Found: C, 86.7; H, 13.2. $C_{15}H_{26}$ requires C, 87.4; H, 12.6 per cent). The higher boiling fraction gave C, 86.8; H, 12.3. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.8 per cent).

Oxidation of Mangiferen with Fuming Nitric Acid.

Concentrated nitric acid having failed to act on it even on heating, 2 g. of mangiferen were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and to the solution (20 c.c.) fuming nitric acid was slowly added with ice cooling and stirring. The reaction mixture was placed on the water-bath for about 30 minutes, taking care that the reaction did not become too vigorous, and then added to excess of cold water. A cream yellow acid separated out which was washed free of nitric acid. It was soluble in dilute alkali, alcohol, ethyl acetate, glacial acetic acid, partly soluble in ether and practically insoluble in petroleum ether and benzene. It could not be crystallised but by purification through alcohol and water its melting point could be raised from 175° to

188° (decomp.). [Found : C, 56.2; H, 6.3; M.W. (cryoscopic in glacial acetic acid), 185. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 7.0 per cent. M.W., 172].

A small quantity of a yellowish semicrystalline powder completely insoluble in benzene also separated from the reaction product, which was insoluble in petroleum ether but soluble in ethyl acetate and melted at 218° (decomp.); racemic *trans*-hexahydrophthalic acid melts at 218°.

Addition of Bromine.

Mangiferen (0.1013 g.) was titrated against bromine in chloroform solution with ice cooling. Following the titration with potassium iodide starch paper, it took 0.0577 g. of bromine as against 0.0537 g. required for one double bond.

Mangiferic Acid (C₄₀H₆₀O₄).

It is a colourless light powder, soluble in benzene, ether, alcohol and insoluble in petroleum ether, m.p. 76-78°. It forms a water-insoluble sodium salt, a gelatinous ammonium salt and ether-soluble lead salt with basic lead acetate. It shows $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +32^\circ$ in 1% absolute alcoholic solution. The air-dried product loses no weight on heating at 110°. In concentrated sulphuric acid it dissolves to a golden yellow solution. [Found : C, 79.0; H, 10.4; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 685. $C_{40}H_{60}O_4$ requires C, 79.5; H, 9.9 per cent. M.W., 604]. Of the two formulae, $C_{40}H_{60}O_4$ and $C_{50}H_{75}O_5$, possible on the basis of the M.W. value, preference has been provisionally given to the former, as parallel M.W. determinations by us, for allied resinous products, showed the error to be invariably on the positive side. Methoxy group was found to be absent in mangiferic acid after Zeisel's method.

On treatment with acetic anhydride and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, mangiferic acid gave a deep red colouration and yielded on dilution a light brown semicrystalline powder, which lost moisture from 108-135°, slowly decomposed from 230° onwards, and appeared to be a diacetyl derivative from its analysis. [Found : C, 76.7; H, 9.8. Diacetyl mangiferic acid ($C_{44}H_{64}O_6$) requires C, 76.7; H, 9.3 per cent. Monoacetyl mangiferic acid ($C_{42}H_{62}O_5$) requires C, 78.0; H, 9.6 per cent].

0.103 G. of mangiferic acid in chloroform solution took 0.0554 g. of bromine in the cold as against 0.0546 g. required for 2 double bonds. The absorption near the end of the titration was comparatively very slow.

Mangiferol (C₂₁H₃₆O₂)₅.

Mangiferol is a sticky, reddish brown product, readily soluble in ether, petroleum ether and benzene, less so in alcohol. It forms a water-soluble sodium salt and an ether-soluble lead salt. It gives phenolic colouration with ferric chloride, but can not be acetylated by the usual method. It absorbs bromine in the cold but can not be hydrogenated in the presence of platinum black. [Found : C, 78·8; H, 11·4; M. W. (cryscopic in benzene), 1632. (C₂₁H₃₆O₂)₅ requires C, 78·8; H, 11·3 per cent. M.W., 1600]. The lead salt, prepared by adding alcoholic lead acetate solution to the alcoholic solution of mangiferol, gave after drying in *vacuo* Pb, 24·3. (C₄₂H₇₀O₄Pb)₅ requires Pb, 24·5 per cent.]. Methoxy group was found to be absent after Zeisel's method.

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